

EDITORIAL

Air Pollution COVID-19 and Forensic Implications

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 and the new variant are a classic example of viral and environmental toxicology link. Observing literature related spread velocity and diffusion of this respiratory virus it is clear the role played by air pollution. The high rate of this environmental pollutant produced a worsening factors that increased mortality rate also.

Two major effect was observed: a proinflammatory effect on the lungs of patient due by the air pollutants like NO₂, Particulate matter and many other typical substance.

A chronic exposition to this toxic produce an inflammatory status as seen in other respiratory classic disease as ASTMA, BCPO and other. Another great contribute is played by the role of CARRIER that PM produces: This particulate matter carry on respiratory tract bioaerosols with viral particle (it seem in a level not able to produce a clinical infection) but also other dangerous substance like BENZO-A-PYRENE.

This substance contribute IL proinflammatory effect and also are able to provide a MUTANT AGENT environment involved also in VARIANT production. (See literature reported).

Many world zone with air pollution was involved in first wave of COVID-19 like Wu-Han but also in north Italy and also involved in VARIANT explosion (MANAUS and other). So we can consider this pathology not only an infectious disease but also an environmental toxicological problem.

Climate change, humidity level, air pollution, UV irradiation, PM, high industrialized regions and other environmental factor are involved in this pathology.

Now are produced vaccines but the emerging of the new variant can be a real problem. But what it is relevant is to recognize also in international world organization that air pollution play a non-secondary role.

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Keywords

- COVID-19 diffusion
- Air pollution
- Environmental toxicology
- Mortality rate
- Worsening factors
- Carriers
- Mutant agent
- Variant
- Social responsibility
- Climate change

INTRODUCTION

Aim of this work is to search relevant literature [1-11] involved in the topics as in keywords.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

With an observational approach some relevant literature related COVID-19, spread, diffusion, air pollution, climate condition, variant and other are analyzed to produce a global conclusion.

RESULTS

After this review it is clear the role played by air pollution in the spread and severity of COVID-19 disease.

BIOLOGY GROUP

VIROLOGY ANTI-ROLOGY BIOLOGY MICROBIOLOGY

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The reported literature from 1 to 11 are a collection of reviews about this topics and it must to be read with great attention by the researchers for the implication also in forensic field.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Because it is clear the link between air pollution and COVID-19 pathology and the global effect on the world population it is needed also to act with an international movement in reducing the global air pollution.

The new variant can come from a natural mutation, or a selection due by various factors (specific immunity measure?) but the presence in PM of mutant agent like Benzo-a pyrene not make we very safety.

The bioaerosols properties, the electrical charger of some respiratory virus, the rapidity of diffusion seem to recognize an airborne properties (especially for some new variant).

This work in the meaning of the author have also a forensic implication because mortality rate was according literature related also parameter like air pollution.

Another fact to be take in consideration is the responsibility of international organization to have considered not airborne a respiratory virus or instead to recognize this properties: For the preventive measure necessary.

Observing the velocity in diffusion of the second wave of COVID-19 it seem not only due by direct contact or by droplets, the same many article was involved in observing the effect of transmission of the virus in indoor places.

The author of this work not think in an individual responsibility but a wider circle: Every reader will produce their opinion and conclusion.

CLARIFICATION

This work is produced under an environmental toxicology point of view not for any diagnostic or therapeutic intent.

This results was presented in 2 international conferences CBCRN Babylon University 2020 and in Liyang-20202nd International Conference on Unlocking Challenges, Innovations and Global Opportunities in Research amidst COVID-19 Pandemic.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

This work is produced in respect of all international rules.

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